

Active Learning in Mathematics Education as a Paradigm Shift for Teaching Generation Z Learners

Aasa, Moses Adebowale

Department of Mathematics, Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate
aasamoses@yahoo.com, +2348030767949

Abstract

One of the objectives of Mathematics Education is to improve the quality and relevance of educational experience of students in order that recognized and measurable learning outcomes are attained, most especially in the area of numeric and functional life skills. This study specifically focused on active learning principle as a paradigm shift for teaching and learning of Mathematics in the age of Generation Z. The study adopts a conceptual research design based on constructivist learning theory that emphasis learner's center and active engagement approaches. It examined what active learning principle, Mathematics and Generation Z is, the connection between Mathematics and Generation Z, fundamental principles to be incorporated into Mathematics classes of Generation Z, and finally strategies, activities, benefits and challenges associated with active learning principle. The study then concludes that active learning principle, if adopted, will help to cater for the needs of Generation Z. It came up with recommendations, among which is the need for Mathematics teachers to promote active engagement, conceptual understanding and positive learning experiences to meet the needs and aspiration of Generation Z.

Keywords: Digital natives, Gamification, Interactive engagement, Real-world connection

For Citation:

Aasa, M. A. (2025). Active learning in mathematics education as a paradigm shift for teaching Generation Z learners. *Journal of Science Scholars*, 3(1), 1–10. [https:// 10.5281/zenodo.15667329](https://10.5281/zenodo.15667329)

Introduction

Education is a tool for socio-economic development of any society as well as individual socio-economic empowerment. The system is vital, because it produces the personnel that are required to function in various facets of developmental process. Educational system unlocks the door to modernization and the teacher holds the key to the door. Educational outcomes include quantifiable knowledge, skills, cognitive understanding, attitudes and proficiencies that students gain from their learning encounters (Mohammed and Jimoh, 2024). The goals of education have changed in recent times to focus on the acquisition of essential needs of Generation Z (Gen Z). These needs define the knowledge and traits necessary to contribute successfully to the workforce and global economy. Describing the different agencies and research groups' findings regarding 21st century skills, Tan, Choo, Kang, and Liem (2017) highlight that innovative, creative, communicative, critical, collaborative and problem-solving are some of the key skills needed to tackle future challenges and contribute meaningfully to the global economy.

For learning to take place, to be meaningful and to bring out desired results in any academic environment, teachers should endeavour to make use of learning strategies that will make the students active when teaching. Active learning is a method of learning in which students are actively or experimentally involved in the learning process. Bonwell and Eison (1991) stated that students participate fully in active learning when they are doing something besides passively listening. Hanson and Moser (2003) believed that using active learning techniques in the classroom can create better academic outcomes for students. Researcher further noted that by utilizing learning strategies such as small-group work, role-play and simulations, data collection and analysis; it is purported to increase students' interest and motivation and build students critical thinking, problem-solving and social skills. In addition to this, active learning can be seen as an instructional approach that is learner-centered in which the students participate or interact with the learning process, rather than passively taking in information. Teachers take the role of facilitators of learning instead of knowledge distributors, hence promote students' performance, engagement, interaction and knowledge retention.

Also, Mathematics has been a crucial component of every advanced society, enabling the development of complex systems and driving progress across the spare of life. It is a fundamental building block that corroborates many aspects of our daily lives, including mobile devices, architecture, art, engineering, finance and even spots (Azuka, 2016). Researchers such as Adenegan (2011), Felda and Cotič (2012), and Bone, Cotič and Felda (2021) opined that Mathematics is indispensable for development of every nation, both as a fundamental element for science, technology and for the development of human beings which involves logical thinking, rationalization, knowledge and application. The need for Mathematics arose because of the increasingly complex demands from societies around the world, which required more advanced mathematical solutions (Wilder, 2013). Solid foundations in Mathematics promote critical thinking, creative, and the ability to solve problems that are necessary for successful living. Aminu (1995) opined that Mathematics is not only the language of sciences but it is an essential nutrient for thought, logic, reasoning and progress.

Generation Z (often shortened to Gen Z, Gen Zers or Zoomers) on the other hand is the demographic cohort succeeding Millennial and preceding Generation Alpha. Merriam-Webster online dictionary defines Gen Z as the generation of people born in the late 1990 and early 2000s. The Collins online dictionaries define Gen Z as members of the generation of people born between the mid-1990 to mid-2010s. The Oxford online dictionary define Gen Z as the group of people who were born between the late 1990s and early 2010s, who are regarded as being very familiar with internet. Encyclopedia Britannica defines Gen Z as the term used to describe Americans born during the late 1990s and early 2000s. Researchers have used the mid-to-late 1990s as starting birth years and the early 2010s as ending birth years to define Gen Z. Although the years spanned is sometimes contested or debated because generations and their zeitgeists are difficult to depict, some sources give the specific year range of 1997-2012.

Despite this argument, members of Gen Z have shaped by the Great Recession of 2007-2009 and the COVID-19 pandemic. They grew up in the era of the iPhone which debuted in 2007. Gen Z is the first true digital native generation. They have lived their lives fully connected digitally. The way they interact with the internet and with each other via the internet is different from the ways of previous generations. To buttress this fact, Yong and Gates (2014) asserted that today's students are not the same as students in the past; they were born in an era where digital technology and the internet are inseparable from human life, and they are more cautious in the career choices (Britannica). From the aforementioned, it is clear that active principle is a teaching and learning conceptual framework that holds the attention of Gen Z students in Mathematics classrooms, because it focuses on students-centered, interactive, and collaborative approaches to promote deep understanding, critical thinking and problem-solving skills. More so, Gen Z is growing up in a world where Mathematics plays a vital role in shaping their daily lives, careers, and future prospects.

Nexus between Mathematics and Gen Z

Everybody, including Gen Z, encounters mathematical concepts in their day-to-day activities such as finances, health, and environmental sustainability. The form of connections or intersections between Mathematics and Gen Z is characterized by the following points:

1. **Digital Natives:** Digital native is used to describe a person who has grown up in the information age. Individuals from these demographic cohorts can quickly and comfortably locate, consume and send digital information through electronic devices and platforms such as computers, mobile phones and social media. They grew up with increased confidence in the technology that they were encircled and engulfed in, which allow them to develop completely different from way of thinking. According to Damayannti, Takaendengan, Kobandaha and Gombah (2023) the accelerated development of technology also affects Mathematics learning. The results of rapid changes in information technologies and technological revolution in Mathematics teaching and learning are represented by modern teaching methods beginning with the scientific calculator, through video teaching tapes, and some other electronics equipment to the computers, and multimedia and programmes (Hamadne and Masaeed, 2015). Nowadays, Damayannti et al

(2023) added that there are a lot of applications that can solve Mathematics problems only by capturing the problems (topics) using Smartphone camera application. Video of Mathematics material also could easily access in YouTube.

2. Data-driven world: Data-driven is a strategy or process that prioritizes data as the main factor in decision-making, using data analysis to guide actions and outcomes (Globant). Also, Bambrick-Santoyo (2010) believe that data-driven instruction is an instructional package that focuses on facts about what students actually learned using data-based methods and not the traditional methods that emphasis what teachers apparently taught in class which base on culture, assessment, analysis and action. According to Kehinde-Dada and Ojo (N.D), data-driven instructional strategy is effective in ameliorating the low performance of learners' achievement in Mathematics. 3.

STEAM careers: Mathematics is a fundamental skill in Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) careers, which are increasingly attractive to Gen Z. The rise of the Gen Z brings with it fresh perspective and attitudes towards various career paths, particularly in the field of STEAM, reveals a complex relationship between interest in STEAM careers and actual career choice which heavily influenced by the level of exposure to STEAM concepts during their formative years (STEAM Ahead, 2024).

4. Problem-solving and Critical Thinking: One of the objectives of Mathematics education in Nigeria as stated by FRN (2014) is that it helps to promote problem-solving, critical thinking and analytical skills which are paramount for Gen Z's future success.

Fundamental Principles to be incorporated into Gen Z Mathematics class

The under listed principles can be incorporated into Gen Z Mathematics classroom for a dynamic learning environment that fosters creativity, critical thinking, and cultural awareness in the era of Gen Z:

1. Student-centered Learning: This is a teaching method that focuses on creating connections with students' interests and the things they learn in school. The ultimate goal is to make the educational process more meaningful to students. The best way to do that is by framing lessons in terms of students' interests, thus encouraging them to engage more in the material and therefore learn better. The ultimate goal of this method is to allow these students to set their own goals, then assess and determine how to achieve them. Hence, students will be able to acquire important and useful skills like analytical thinking, problem-solving, creativity and leadership.

2. Interactive Engagement: Interactive engagement in Mathematics class is a teaching method that engages students in Mathematics in a more hands-on way. It's active participation in Mathematics versus passive participation and an exploration of Mathematics through dynamic means like games, manipulative and digital tools. Mathematics can be a challenging subject for many Gen Zers because of its abstract nature which lead to frustration and gaps in understanding of foundational concepts. This method will help the students to enhanced understanding, increased engagement, multi-sensory learning, real-world application, improvised retention, collaboration and communication, reduced Mathematics anxiety and supports differentiated instruction.

3. **Collaborative Learning:** This is an umbrella term used to refer to a variety of educational approaches involving a joint intellectual effort by either students or both students and teachers together. Usually, this joint intellectual effort involves students working together in peer-to-peer, or groups of two or more people, individually searching for understanding, solutions or meaning. The collaborative learning strategy gives students direct experimental encounters with real-world problems. Hence it develops problem-solving abilities, understanding of complex relationship as well as decision making abilities.
4. **Real-world connection:** This is an academic technique that supports students learning gains by incorporating real-world examples. This exciting and practical ways of teaching can be applied to Gen Z Mathematics classrooms to give students a well-rounded approach that supports learning connections by connecting mathematical concepts to everyday life, careers and societal issues. Connecting the real-world to content standard is beneficial for students, teachers and society because it fosters a natural learning environment. When real-world learning are applied, students can see that the information they learn is practical, applicable and relevant to their lives. Involving students in a real-world way helps build up confidence, refine problem-solving skills, and promotes a sense of belonging that goes far beyond the classrooms setting. Even if a student dislike the subject (Mathematics) he/she can still see the value in connecting real-world examples to it. When students connect real-life with classroom content, it helps them authentically engage and gain knowledge which will foster deeper understanding, engagement, and retention of knowledge.
5. **Technology-enhanced learning:** This is a new era of learning that utilizes mobile technologies to enable individuals to seamlessly move between physical, digital and communicative spaces for educational purposes. With this, the Zers students will be able to learn where and when is best for them, be engaging and finally learn at their own pace, because Gen Z expects to use technology such as mobile devices, laptops, and learning management system, to support their mathematical learning.
6. **Feedback and reflection:** Effective feedback and reflection with continuous assessment and self-improvement plays a crucial role in fostering growth, development and success for Gen Z. Understanding their preferred communication styles, such as instant messaging and collaborative platforms, lays the foundation for effective feedback delivery. The teacher should make sure that he/she provide Gen Z with tools or frameworks that enable them to evaluate their performance and identify areas for improvement. This in turn empower Gen Z to take ownership of their development and actively seek feedback which promotes continuous learning.

Active Learning Strategies

Some active learning strategies that Mathematics teachers can employ in order to cope with Gen Z students in Mathematics include:

1. **Flipped classroom:** A flipped classroom is an instructional strategy and type of blended learning that aims to increase student engagement and learning by having students work on live problem-solving during class time. With this, students watch online lectures, collaborates in online discussions, or solving Mathematics manipulative at home, while actively engaging concepts in

the classroom with a teacher guidance. The flipped classroom shift instruction is a learner-centered model in which students are often initially introduced to new topics outside of school, freeing up classroom time for the exploration of topics in greater depth, creating meaningful learning opportunity. In this strategy, students are actively involved in knowledge acquisition and construction as they participate in and evaluate their learning (Alvarez, 2011; Fungi, 2020).

2. **Project-based learning:** This is an instructional approach designed to give students the opportunity to develop knowledge and skills through engaging projects set around challenges and problems they may face in real world. In this method, students work on a Mathematics problem over an extended period of time that engages them in solving a real-world problem or answering a complex question. They demonstrate their knowledge and skills by creating presentation for a real audience. As a result, students develop deep content knowledge as well as critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication skills.

3. **Problem-based learning:** This is a teaching method in which students learn about Mathematics through the experience of solving an open-ended problem. This method does not focus on problem solving with a defined solution, but it allows for the development of desirable skills such as knowledge acquisition, enhanced group, collaboration and communication (wikipedia). This method is self-directed and student-centered way of learning which aims to put students' knowledge into practice which provide an opportunity for students to build conceptual understanding. Problem-based tasks require students to apply their current understanding and skills to new contexts that could be solved with multiplication before they have formally been taught what multiplication is and how it works, they build an understanding that multiplication is repeated addition.

4. **Gamification:** This is an attempt to enhance systems, services, organizations, and activities by simulating experiences similar to those experienced when playing games in order to motivate and engage the students to actively participate in their mathematical journey. This method enables the teacher to teach Mathematics with fun and make Mathematics play rather than work. The gamification of Mathematics lessons happens when you identify where Mathematics occurs in either actual games or in the world around you using Mathematics as the foundation.

5. **Peer instruction and assessment:** This is a method that provides a structured learning process for students to critique and provide feedback to each other on their work. It helps students to develop lifelong skills in assessing and providing feedback to others, and also equips themselves with skills to self-assess and improve their work. With this method, students will be able to take responsibility to manage their own learning, learn to assess and give others constructive feedback to develop lifelong assessment skills and enhance students' learning through knowledge diffusion and exchange of ideas.

Active Learning Activities

The question now is, what are the active learning activities that will be useful for this generation? For Gen Z to acquire necessary skill in Mathematics class, teachers should try as much as possible to embark on but not limited to the following active learning activities:

1. **Mathematics scavenger hunts:** This is a game based on a search for a list of items in other to motivate students to review mathematical concepts. Students will be challenged to find examples of mathematical concepts like counting, shapes or fractions in everyday objects. This real-world approach to Mathematics is a perfect way to incorporate STEAM learning into Gen Z life and making abstract nature of Mathematics concretes and allow the students work at their own pace. Since it is a collaborative activity, the students can help each other to complete their lists.
2. **Real-world-problem-solving challenges:** This is what we do every day. It requires flexibility, resilience, resourcefulness, and a certain degree of creativity. This method require that the students should involves themselves with continuous interaction with the environment during the problem-solving process. The environment is not only seen as a source of inspiration but also as a tool to facilitate creative thinking. To demonstrate this, there is a story of Archimedes (287-212) having said to Hieron King of Syracuse *“give me a place to stand and I will move the earth.”* He realized that a man of modest strength could move a very great weight if he was assisted by the leverage afforded by a very long arm. Without full understanding of this principle, Hieron demanded of Archimedes that he gives an illustration of his ideas. As a practical illustration of the idea, Archimedes arranged a lever system so that Hieron himself could move a larger and fully laden ship (Krantz, 2006).
3. **Mathematics modeling competitions:** Mathematical modeling is defined as a process of representing real world problems in mathematical terms in an attempt to understand and find solutions to the problems (Keng, 2010). This method allows students to form themselves in a contests challenge teams to analyze, formulate theories, solve, and present solution reports to an open-ended application problem. It is also a fun and intense opportunity to use mathematical skills to solve real-world problems and perform better in Mathematics.
4. **Debates and Mathematics discussion:** Mathematics teachers should try as much as possible to discover how to create structured debates in Mathematics class that make Mathematics concepts more engaging and relatable for students. To create debatable moments in Mathematics class, teacher needs to open questions to students’ opinions and give students a chance to have something to say. Teacher should try to have open-ended questions (those with more than one answer) and opinion-ended questions that is, questions that allow for students to develop arguments.
5. **Mathematics games and puzzles:** This is an arithmetic value expressed by a word, symbol or figure, representing a particular quantity and used in counting and making calculations.

Benefits of Active Learning Strategy and Activities for Gen Z in Mathematics Lesson

The gains of applying active learning principle and activities for Gen Z in Mathematics class are:

1. It will increase Gen Z engagement;
2. It will improve problem-solving skills;
3. The rate at which the students will collaborate and communicate will be high;
4. It will automatically lead to deepen understanding of mathematical concepts;
5. The students have better chance to prepare for real-world applications of what they have learnt;

6. It will develop level of critical thinking and creativity;
7. The teacher-students relationship will be improved, and,
8. The students will be confident to face difficult task.

Challenges of using Active Learning Principle in Mathematics classroom for Gen Z

The stumbling blocks on the way of using active learning principle in Mathematics classroom for Gen Z include:

1. There is little or no training for Mathematics teachers to support the principle;
2. Inadequate resources in terms of technology and time;
3. Since teaching is not static, there is problem of dynamics classroom managing;
4. There is problem of balancing structure and flexibility on the part of subject teachers;
5. There is problem of addressing diverse learning needs;
6. Ensuring equity and inclusion is also posing a treat;
7. Lack of the required knowledge to manage technology distractions, and,
8. Lastly, assessing and evaluating the students learning using this principle is not easy.

Conclusion

The relevance of adopting active learning principle in teaching students in this age of Gen Z in Mathematics class is so enormous that one cannot afford to underplay its usefulness. To this end, by adopting active learning principle, educators can create an engaging, effective, and students-centered Mathematics class that caters for the unique characteristics of Gen Z students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Relevant stakeholders should implement programmes to enhance active learning principle in terms of resources, and creating supportive peer network for students within the school environment.
2. Relevant agencies should prioritize and adopt active teaching method that promote reasoning and understanding in Mathematics class.
3. Mathematics teachers should promote active engagement, conceptual understanding, and positive learning experiences.
4. Mathematics teachers should go for regular training and professional development in terms of seminars and workshop to enhance their pedagogical skills and promote positive attitude towards the subject.

References

- Adenegan, K. E. (2011). Setting Mathematics Laboratory in Schools. <https://www.sub.qucosa.de/api/qucosa%3A1877/attachment/ATT-01>.
- Alvarez, B. (2011). Flipping the Classroom: Homework in Class, Lessons at home. Education Digest: Essential Readings Condensed for Quick Review, 77 (8), 18-21.
- Aminu, J. (1995). Quality and Stress in Nigeria Education. Kano, Northern Publishing Company.

- Azuka, B. F. (2016). *Mathematics in Nigeria Secondary School. A Teaching Perspective*. Port-Harcourt. Rex-Charles and Patrick Ltd.
- Bambrick-Santoyo, P. (2010). *Driven by Data. A practical guide to improve instruction*.
- Bone, J., Cotič, M. & Felda, D. (2021). Justifying in Mathematics Lessons *Pedagogical Horizons*, 36 (1), 33-52.
- Bonwell, C. & Eison, J. (1991). *Active Learning: Creating Excitement in the Classroom* AEHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No.1. Washington D. C.: Jossey-Bass. ISBN 978-1-878380-08-1
- Damayanti, T, Takaendengan, B.R., Kobandaha, P. E. & Gombah, W. (2023). Digital Natives Preferences in How to Learn Mathematics: A Qualitative Study of Preservice Mathematics Teachers. *Jambura Journal of Mathematics Education*, 4 (1), 75-80.
- Encyclopedia Britannica. Definition of Generation Z. <https://www.britannica.com>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). National Policy on Education. NERDC Abuja
- Felda, D. & Cotič, M. (2012). Why Teach Mathematics? *Journal of Elementary Education*, 5 (2/3), 107-120.
- Fungi, C. H. (2020). How does flipping classroom foster the STEM Education: A case study of the FPN model, *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 25 (3), 479-507.
- Globant @ <https://www.globant.com>
- Hamadneh, I. M. & Masaeed, A. A. (2015). Mathematics Teachers attitudes towards photo Mathematics Application in solving mathematical problem using mobile camera. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 10 (14).
- Hanson, S. & Moser, S. (2003). Reflections on a discipline-wide Project: Developing A. L. modules on the Human Dimensions of global changes. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 27 (1), 17-38.
- Jossey-Brassa Wiley Imprint 989 market, San Francisco, CA94103-1741.
- Kehinde-Dada, O. V. and Ojo, A. A. (N.D). Effects of Data-Driven Instruction as a Teaching Strategy on Junior Secondary School Students' Classroom Participation in Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Theory and Practice of Educational Research*, 51-63.
- Keng, K. C. (2010). Teaching and Learning Mathematical Modelling with Technology. Available at <https://atc.mathandtech.org>, 21/1/2025
- Krantz, S. G. (2006). *An Episodic History of Mathematics: Mathematical Culture through Problem Solving*, pp. 21-23.
- Merriam-Webster online Dictionary. Definition of Generation Z. <https://www.merriam-webster.com>
- Mohammed, A. O. & Jimoh, A. S. (2024). Predictive Role of Active Learning Strategies on learning outcomes in Economics among Public Secondary School Students in Lagos State, Nigeria. *LASU International Journal of Arts*, 2 (1).
- STEAM Ahead (2024). Gen Z and STEM Careers: How Exposure Influences @ <https://www.westeamahead.org>.
- Tan, J. P. L., Choo, S. S., Kang, T. & Liem, G. A. D. (2017). Educating for Twenty-first Century competencies and future- ready learners: Research perspectives from Singapore. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*. 37 (4), 425-436.
- The Collins online Dictionary. Generation Z. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com>
- The Oxford online Dictionary. Definition of Generation Z. <https://www.oed.com>
- Wikipedia: Problem-based Learning; <https://en.wikipedia.org>.

Wilder, R. L. (2013). *Evolution of Mathematical Concepts*. Dover Publication.

Yong, S. & Gates, P. (2104). Born Digital: Are they really digital natives. *International Journal of e-education, e-Business, e-Management and e-Learning*, 4 (2), 102-105.